

**FOOD, HEALTH AND ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH
INFRASTRUCTURES TO TACKLE EMERGING PRIORITIES**

Deliverable 1.4

Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of Results

TECHNICAL REFERENCES

Grant Agreement number: 101131588

Project website: <https://fheritale.eu/>

Lead Beneficiary: Instruct-ERIC

Contractual delivery date: June 2024

Actual delivery date: 28/06/2024

Type and dissemination level: R / PU

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1. Executive Summary

This document defines a targeted outreach programme and communication plan for the FHERITALE project. The document also provides tools, guidelines and materials to be used in the implementation of this communication plan.

2. Introduction

The FHERITALE project seeks to provide the European research community with a comprehensive overview of technologies and services relevant to investigate the effects on health and the environment that artificial materials (including plastics, micro-, nano-, and biotechnological materials) can have. The objectives include the provision of a landscape of the currently available services, the definition of the research areas to target (as well as any gaps and specific technological needs), and setting out strategies for long-term sustainability of these services into the future. This will result in a catalogue of services being made available to food, health, and environmental researchers as well as to targeted stakeholders. This catalogue will be a central source to access the technologies required for this life-critical research.

To reach these ambitious objectives, a stringent communications plan is required. Its outputs will be of particular relevance, providing a clear and centralised source of information on where to access the relevant services in this field. The impact of artificial materials on food, health, and environmental is a global issue, both geographically and politically – it is of interest to all. In FHERITALE, Tasks 1.2 and 2.2 focus on the development of networking and outreach activities to engage all relevant stakeholders respectively in period 1 and 2 of the project. Activities will leverage on the expertise of both CIRMMP and Instruct-ERIC, with input from all project partners, to ensure engagement of the relevant scientific communities with the catalogue of services, and reports from the landscaping activities.

3. Communications Plan

Aims of the Communication Plan and Strategy

The overall goal of the communication strategy is to increase the visibility of the results of the project and facilitate greater integration of the central research communities. As such, Tasks 1.2 and 2.2 aims at accomplishing the following goals:

- Outreach and communication activities of the FHERITALE project outcomes to maximise the engagement with relevant stakeholders;
- Implementation of a portfolio of activities to manage and monitor internal and external communication of FHERITALE to all stakeholders with the aim of explaining the ambition and objectives of the project in a consistent manner;
- Designing and open a project website to inform general public about goals and achievements of the project;

- Outreach activities including specific events organised within the frame of FHERITALE as well as engagement in third-party events (ICRI, ERIC Forum, HE projects).

To achieve these aims, the present communication plan outlines the following actions:

- Raise awareness of the FHERITALE consortium and its activities;
- Increase the broader life science community’s understanding of the involvement of RIs in the study of artificial materials and their impact on food, health, and the environment;
- Ensure adherence to FHERITALE branding and establish a clear consistent style;
- Regularly evaluate the impacts of the various communication channels and tools used;
- Create a space on the website to outline and display project outcomes and achievements.

Audiences and Stakeholders

FHERITALE has a clear objective, but to reach this must receive input from (and report back out to) a variety of stakeholders:

- The research infrastructure community;
- Academy and research;
- Food System Business Operators;
- EU and the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI);
- General public and media.

The key communication messages directed at each external audience are summarised in the table below:

Audience	Key message
Research Infrastructure Community	The FHERITALE project will highlight the impact of cooperation of different research infrastructures in tackling a common and urgent problem. This stakeholder will be responsible for inputting much of the information and direction of the FHERITALE project, and so will receive the results to distribute further to their own research communities.
Academic and industry researchers	The central aim of FHERITALE is to develop an easily accessible and usable catalogue of services and technologies available for academic and industrial researchers to work on food, health and environmental research. Once this repository has been established, the wider research community will need to be informed quickly, repeatedly, and thoroughly, to efficiently communicate the benefits to them, and outline the opportunities available.
EU/ESFRI	FHERITALE will boost collaboration opportunities, excellence in science, competitiveness and impact at national, European and

	international levels - aiming to work with policy makers to disseminate results to relevant authorities.
General public	FHERITALE will exploit project results to respond to current and future food, health, and environmental needs, and aware society about this important challenge

Communication Materials

FHERITALE will use several channels of communication to reach different audiences and users, as summarised in the matrix below:

Type	Channel	Primary audience(s)*	Intended reach	Intended frequency of communication	Management	Resourcing
Website	News	EC, RC, CP, LSC, GP	International	Monthly	Instruct team	Low
	Events	EC, RC, CP, LSC, GP	International	Monthly	Instruct team	Low
	General information	GP	International	When needed	Instruct team	Low
	Success stories and service catalogue	EC, RC, CP, LSC, GP	International	When available	Instruct team	Medium
Social media	X (formerly Twitter)	EC, RC, CP, LSC, GP	International	Weekly	Instruct team	Low
	LinkedIn	EC, RC, CP, LSC	International	Weekly	Instruct team	Low
Mailing lists	Internal	CP	Individuals	When needed	Instruct team	Low
	External	RC, LSC	Individuals	When needed	Instruct team	Low
Publications	Scientific journals	LSC, RC	International	When available	Consortium Partners	Moderate
Events	FHERITALE Events	EC, RC, CP, LSC	International	Regular	Instruct and CIRMMP teams	High
	Partner events &	EC, RC, CP, LSC	International	When available	Consortium Partners	High

	external conferences					
Media	News outlets	GP	International	When needed	Instruct team	Moderate to high

*European Commission (EC), research community (RC), EU/ESFRI and life science community (LSC), general public (GP), consortium partners (CP)

Website

The most critical communication channel is the FHERITALE website, hosted at <https://fheritale.eu>. The website serves as the central point for all communication activities – all users are directed to the website to acquire any information they need about the project. All further communication channels used by FHERITALE will also direct users to the website. The header menu and footer on the website’s homepage contain redirects to all information on the website (Figure 1). The header menu currently contains links to the homepage, the ‘About’ page (with a dropdown to pages for ‘Governance’, ‘Work Packages’, and ‘Partners’. Pages for ‘News and Events’, ‘Contact’ and ‘Internal’ link to the FHERITALE Shared Folder. In the website footer, links to the home, about and contact details for the project.

Of the two press releases planned for the project (M1 and M30), the first has already been completed, outlining the scope of the project and a review of the kick off meeting.

Figure 1: Website homepage

Social Media

FHERITALE project communication is supported by two social media accounts, one for X (formerly Twitter) and one for LinkedIn (Figures 2 and 3).

Figure 2. FHERITALE X account page

Figure 3. FHERITALE LinkedIn Account, home page

The primary aim of both social media channels is to extend the reach of the project, engage more users and stakeholders, and redirect audiences to the project website for more information. This social media-based outreach will be particularly important before events (to build interest and maximise registration), during events (to provide live updates and engagement) and after events (provide updates on meetings).

Mailing Lists

Internal Mailing Lists

For maximum engagement and understanding from partners, internal mailing lists must be used wisely and efficiently to inform project partners of the latest news and developments. In particular, communications officers of partner teams must remain informed, so they may update the rest of their Hubs and directly begin to disseminate information through their own channels.

External Mailing Lists

Through the website, networking events and other channels, a mailing list for external users can be developed. This mailing list can then be used to disseminate important information about FHERITALE directly to the target audience. This channel can also be used to disseminate the newsletter.

Partner Mailing Lists

Project news and events should be disseminated by partner mailing lists to their own communities to boost engagement. Content can be disseminated internally to all partners, then distributed through partner mailing lists to their subscribers for wider reach. This requires input from the communications officers/teams from all partners.

Meetings and Conferences

FHERITALE will organise events throughout the course of the project. Such events are an opportunity to promote the project directly to target audiences and explain in greater detail the aims and outcomes of FHERITALE.

Activities will also aim at exploiting potential synergies with relevant EU projects, organisations and networks.

When relevant, events will be adapted to the hybrid model, enabling both physical and virtual attendance and thus making the project message accessible to a wider audience.

As well as events organised by the FHERITALE consortium, it is important that partners take the opportunity to present the project at external conferences and events, to engage new stakeholders. Poster sessions and talks at relevant events are an important tool in external communication.

Templates, Style, and Branding

Templates for communication activities and reports will be made available under the ‘Communication and Outreach’ section of the FHERITALE Google Drive shared folder. Here, consortium partners may access templates for Word documents, deliverables and presentations, which should be used for all internal and external communication.

The FHERITALE logo is also available for download via the FHERITALE Google Drive shared folder. The colours used are #91C46E for the logo outline (the brackets), #4B77A7 for the logo text and a gradient of #C4D0E2 to #F5DAE9 for the “Fairy” wings. Reports documents, presentation templates and any other material related to FHERITALE are to be branded with this logo and colour scheme, offering a distinctive project identity. The logo in all necessary formats is shown in Figure 4 below:

Figure 4: All forms of the FHERITALE logo, which will be available to internal users

Boilerplate Text

To unify the message of FHERITALE and facilitate written communication with audiences, the following text may be used to describe the project and its aims:

Exposure to artificial materials, either as a result of their intended use (e.g.: food packaging) or at the end of their lifecycle (e.g. plasticware) can have a profound impact on human health either directly, or through the food we eat, or the environment we live in. The FHERITALE project seeks to provide the European research community with a comprehensive overview of technologies and services relevant to understanding this impact. These services are expected to span multiple scales and disciplines, including high-quality metrology, structural biology, microbiology, and ecotoxicology. FHERITALE's objectives include analysing the current landscape of available services, also beyond its partnership, identifying gaps, and engaging with stakeholders in the research community.

Next Steps

The material and tools described in this document have been provided to all partners to maximise outreach activities and increase the visibility of the consortium and its work. Instruct-ERIC will coordinate the outreach and dissemination activities, with support from consortium partners. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for outreach have been established and will be monitored throughout the project:

KPI description	Target
Consortium and stakeholders' events	4
Participation to workshops/conferences/industry fairs/exhibitions/open days/public events	30
Participation in initiatives jointly organised with other EU/National projects	6
Webinars	6
Communication tool kit (Poster, roll-up, brochures, flyers)	1
Press releases	2
Infographics	2
Scientific publications (review papers)	3

These KPIs will be regularly monitored to ensure that project communications is running as anticipated.